

Iraqi EFL Teachers' and Learners' Attitude toward the Use of Technological Tools in EFL Class Room

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 19, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : EFL Teachers, learners, Technology, Attitude</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4618393</p>	<p><i>This study has attempted to investigate Iraqi EFL teachers' and learners' attitudes toward the use of technology in EFL classes. The participants were 20 male and female English teachers with the age range of 30-45 and 50 male and female intermediate learners, with the age range of 12-18. Based on Br (2001) and Dörnyei' (2010) guidelines, the questionnaire was developed and validated. For accepting the construct validity in the Iraq context, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) based on the Structural Equation Model: SEM using the LISREL (8.5) software was done. Results showed that the value of t-statistic in all cases was greater than 1.96 or less than -1.96, so it could be concluded that the questions of the questionnaire provided a suitable factor structure for measuring the dimensions studied in the research model. And also the values for the fit indices, RMSEA was 0.077 and smaller than 0.08, so this model is acceptable. The value of Chi-square meant that χ^2/DF (equal 2.74, and is between 1 - 3. The value of CFI, IFI, GFI, NFI was larger than 0.9. The Cronbach's alpha obtained for the questionnaire was 0.799, which is higher than 0.7, so the reliability of the questionnaire could be confirmed. The result showed that educational technology was effective for teachers. The data indicated that educational technology was effective on learners.</i></p>

Introduction

Technology is a fact of life as the medium of daily communication affecting language learning. Today's young generation is called the net generation because technologies are the most familiar items for them (Eckhaus & Davidovitch, 2019). Hernandez-de-Menendez and Morales-Menendez (2019) stated that this net generation has been found to be applied in different methods of learning from the earlier generation. The new generation is more engaged and constantly connected to the net. It is believed that net generation students prefer independent learning style and have stronger beliefs in technologies for better learning.

The use of modern technology in teaching English is broadly understood to encompass an innovative application of methods, tools, materials, devices, systems, and strategies which are directly relevant to English language teaching and lead to the achievement of the desired goals. Thus, while technology is now generally accepted as an important educational tool across a range of teaching and learning contexts, it is particularly true of English language teaching since it affords a number of potential opportunities to enhance both the content and delivery of the pedagogies typically associated with traditional English language instruction (Lawless & Pellegrino, 2007).

The use of technology in teaching English consolidates the integrated view of the modern means system and association with other components which benefits students by achieving the required results (Khan, Bibi, & Hasan, 2016). It is essential that the education sector keep apace of the global technological revolution by adopting modern technological means such as computerization, multi-media devices, mobile phones, audio/visual effects applications, and social media, to optimize English language instruction and equip teachers to connect with classroom language learners in a systematic and advanced way. Therefore, it should be considered that teachers often play a key role in operating the different tools and teaching methods (Peralta & Costata, 2007).

If the goal is to promote technology enhanced education, it is of primary importance to investigate what teachers perceive of technology and its use in education, what their knowledge and skills are or what skills they need to further develop. The teacher factor is yet to be resolved, thus continuing to draw the attention of educational researchers, teacher educators, curriculum developers and stakeholders in promoting educational reform (Baran & Uygun, 2016). Various studies conducted in various settings continue to add to the literature on technology integration by rendering perspectives on the complex issue of teacher characteristics, influential in technology use. Uncovering common patterns related with the teacher factor may enable taking joint action or

simply, be inspiring and directive for those responsible for transforming education in their contexts (Ventayen, 2019).

There is a need therefore for a research position on this study. Previous studies have investigated age and ICT-related behaviors of teachers in primary and secondary schools; few have carried out this study on teachers of teachers whose behaviors would model that of their trainees. It is on this note that the present study seeks to investigate the effect of clip learning through telegram aiming at reducing the stress and negative attitude of teachers toward digital innovations in EFL classrooms, so the researcher was interested to take up this study. Moreover this study is going to design a model and a questionnaire for assessing the Iraqi EFL learners' and teachers' attitudes towards using technology in teaching and learning English as a foreign language.

The limitations of the study were as following: First of all, because of feasibility consideration convenience sampling was applied for selecting the participants. Secondly, the study will be conducted only in language institute.

Apart from designing and validating a questionnaire, this study was an attempt to answer the following questions:

1. What is Iraqi EFL teachers' attitude toward the use of technology in EFL class?
2. What is Iraqi EFL learners' attitude toward the use of technology in EFL class?

Accordingly, the following research hypotheses were raised to address the aforementioned gap:

1. Technology has no significant effect on Iraqi EFL teachers' attitudes.
2. Technology has no significant effect on Iraqi EFL learners' attitudes.

2. Review of the Related Literature

Technology

The use of technology for instructional purposes goes back to the 20th century with the introduction of educational films. The concept of visual instruction was established at the beginning of 1920. In 1946, the University of Pennsylvania has used the first electronic computer. In 1960, computer-based education was influenced throughout the world. During this period, the learners could access resources through the use of linked computer terminals that the University of Illinois launched in the classroom. This was done while listening to the lecture that was recorded via a linked device like a television or audio device (Eckhaus & Davidovitch, 2019). In 1970, the mouse, hypertext and groupware were invented by Engelbart who created also the hypermedia, multiple-window screens and electronic mail system. Between the 1970s and 1980s microprocessors and electronic books have been introduced. Personal computers, video cassette recorders and CD-Rom were available (Hernandez-de-Menendez & Morales-Menendez, 2019).

For Luppacini (2005), technology refers to both "material construction as well as the intellectual and social contexts... it refers to the organization of knowledge for the achievement of practical purposes as well as any tool or technique of doing or making, by which capability is extended" (p. 104).

Technology facilitates the storage, transmission, and retrieval of information in multimedia on an individualized, interactive basis (Romano, 2003). The use of multimodal technology in language studies is a cost-effective and highly stimulating way to achieve the goal of acquiring a second language, however, research shows that teachers have widely varying responses to the adoption of integrated technology (for example, Tong & Trinidad, 2005).

The use of technology in the classroom reflects benefits for both the teacher and learner. Technology will provide the learners with different activities that will help them to learn more about the target language and practice it as well. It means wider access to information and the improvement of skills. (Rodinadze & Zarbazoya, 2012).

Empirical studies on

Mussa (2020) investigate the E-learning motivations of Iraqi secondary students in Malaysia in order to support the Iraqi educational organizations of E-learning adopting. The significance result showed that the students have enough motivation to use E-learning services instead of the current learning system in their school.

Jassim and Dzakiria (2018) investigated to elicit Iraqi students' attitudes on using video to develop English learning. In addition, it aimed to discover the impact of using video on learning English skills. The results of this research indicated that the students were in favor of video's potential for developing English language proficiency. Video was a fun element to use, and most significant of all, the students feel that it was a new substitute way to learn English and needs to be taking more interest in the education system.

In another study, Xodabande (2018) explored Iranian EFL learners' preferences regarding the use of different digital technologies for language learning beyond the classroom and their beliefs on how these technologies augment their language skills. . Findings of the study indicate that despite some imposed restrictions on social

network and Internet use in Iran, most Iranian EFL learners are actively using them in their language learning beyond the classroom.

Jang (2008) examined the effect of integrating technology with teaching strategies. The findings indicated that teachers who use ICT could utilize the various technologies and instructional theories; whereas traditional teachers demonstrated less integration of ICT and instructional theories. The study indicates that applying ICT and the integration of teaching strategies in the teacher education courses had an important influence on the pre-service teachers' ability to utilize technology for their teaching purpose.

3. Method

Participants and setting

a questionnaire for exploring the Iraqi EFL learners' and teachers' attitude toward applying technology in the class, was 20 male and female English teachers with the age range of 30-45 and 50 male and female intermediate learners, with the age range of 12-18.

Instrument

Based on Br (2001) and Dörnyei' (2010) guidelines, the questionnaire was developed and validated. For accepting the construct validity in Iraq context, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) based on the Structural Equation Model: SEM using the LISREL (8.5) software was done. Results showed that the value of t-statistic in all cases was greater than 1.96 or less than -1.96, so it could be concluded that the questions of the questionnaire provided a suitable factor structure for measuring the dimensions studied in the research model. And also the values for the fit indices, RMSEA was 0.077 and smaller than 0.08 but this model acceptable. The value of Chi-square meant that χ^2/DF (equal 2.74, and is between 1 - 3. The value of CFI, IFI, GFI, NFI was larger than 0.9. . The Cronbach's alpha obtained for the questionnaire was 0.799, which is higher than 0.7, so the reliability of the questionnaire could be confirmed.

Procedure

The qualitative data of the study were collected from students and teachers through a questionnaire for the purpose of categorizing the responses of the participants. The goal of the questionnaire was to understand the participants' attitudes toward using technology in English classes. Therefore, the model concerning Iraqi EFL teachers, and learners' attitudes towards using technology in teaching was design based on following model.

Figure 1. The process of developing the models

Results

1. Confirmatory factor analysis of the construct validity

For accepting the construct validity in Iraq context, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) based on the Structural Equation Model: SEM using the LISREL (8.5) software was done. The overall theory behind the SEM was like regression analysis; however, it had some advantages over it. First, it takes into account the errors. Second, more than one dependent variable can be examined at the same time. And finally, it also examines the relationships between independent variables. Moreover, the relationships between observed and latent variables can be examined. In the end, model fit is assessed using goodness of fit indices. In the present study, χ^2/df , GFI, AGFI, CFI, IFI, NFI, and RMSEA were used. To have a fit model for confirmation, first of all t-value should be significant, it means that at 95 confidence level, t-value should be larger than 1.96 or smaller than -1.96 ($t > 1.96$ or $t < -1.96$) and also has Fitting indexes. Indexes used are Chi – square which value should be between 1-3, Root mean squared error of approximation (RMSEA) which the value 0.08 is acceptable, and other indexes such as Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), Goodness – for- fit index (GFI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normal Fit Index (NFI), the value should be larger than 0.9.

The chart of Confirmatory Factor Analysis that is Path Coefficients and T-value (chart one and two) has been shown in which:

X1: I am interested in using technology, X2: I'd call myself a risk-taker, X3: I like to practice English the way native speakers do, X4: By technology, I find it easy to put myself in other people's shoes and imagine how they feel, X5: I find it hard to make conversation even with people who speak my own language but after practicing English by using technology this feeling changed.

Chi-Square=1110.38, df=405, P-value=0.00000, RMSEA=0.077

Figure 1: Path Coefficients

Chi-Square=1110.38, df=405, P-value=0.00000, RMSEA=0.077

Figure2: t-value

In relation to figures 1 and 2, the results had been shown in following tables. Table 1 showed that the value of t-statistic in all cases was greater than 1.96 or less than -1.96, so it could be concluded that the questions of the questionnaire provided a suitable factor structure for measuring the dimensions studied in the research model.

Table 1: Results of the CFA

questions	Path Coefficients	t-value
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Q1	0.45	10.15
Q2	0.41	10.23
Q3	0.45	9.08
Q4	0.44	9.24
Q5	0.53	9.98
Q6	0.50	10.33
Q7	0.59	11.81
Q8	0.50	9.66
Q9	0.54	11.52
Q10	0.52	9.60
Q11	0.45	5.50
Q12	0.45	9.55
Q13	0.44	7.20
Q14	0.47	7.81
Q15	0.46	7.68
Q16	0.43	9.70
Q17	0.50	10.87
Q18	0.47	8.08
Q19	0.60	12.02
Q20	0.53	11.03
Q21	0.52	11.07
Q22	0.62	12.74
Q23	0.63	12.16
Q24	0.55	10.15
Q25	0.51	10.41
Q26	0.69	12.47
Q27	0.63	13.01
Q28	0.54	11.45
Q29	0.47	9.28
Q30	0.59	10.04

Table 2 also showed the values for the fit indices, RMSEA was 0.077 and smaller than 0.08 but this model acceptable. The value of Chi-square meant that χ^2/DF (equal 2.74, and is between 1 - 3. The value of CFI, IFI, GFI, NFI was larger than 0.9.

Therefore, in general, it could be said that the values of the indicators corresponded to their interpretive criteria and confirmatory factor analysis confirmed the structure of the questionnaire.

Table 2: Goodness-of-fit indices

χ^2/DF	RMSEA	NFI	GFI	IFI	CFI	AGFI
2.74	0.077	0.93	0.91	0.92	0.93	0.94

- Reliability questionnaire (Reliability)

Reliability is a technical feature of a measuring instrument. This concept deals with the extent to which measuring instruments produce the same results under the same conditions.

The reliability coefficient range was from zero to one. The closer this coefficient was to one, the more reliable the questionnaire was. In this study, Cronbach's alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the test. This method was used to calculate the internal consistency of a measuring instrument that measures different properties. If the alpha value was greater than 0.7, it indicated good reliability, and if it was between 0.5 and 0.7, it indicated moderate reliability. In the present study, in order to determine the reliability of the questionnaire and its dimensions, Cronbach's alpha value was calculated using SPSS software. The results were shown in the table below. As could be seen in the table below, the Cronbach's alpha obtained for the questionnaire was 0.799, which is higher than 0.7, so the reliability of the questionnaire could be confirmed.

Table 3: Reliability Statistics

N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
30	0.799

Descriptive Statistics

The tendency to learn after using technology had increased among female learners than male learners.

Figure 2: Language Learning Attitudes (Students)

The desire to learn after using technology had increased among female teachers than male teachers.

Figure 3: Language Learning Attitudes (Teachers)

Figure 4: Language Learning Attitudes (Teachers)

3. 20 language learners and 50 teachers were present in the present study, of which 12 language learners are males (8 girls) and 25 male teachers (25 women).

Figure 5: Student & Sex

Figure 8: Teachers & Sex

Inferential Statistics:

Test of normality

To implement statistical methods and calculate appropriate test statistics and logical inferences about research hypotheses, the most important step before any action was to choose the appropriate statistical method for research. For this purpose, knowledge of data distribution was a top priority. The statistical hypotheses of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test were as follows.

H₀: The data are normally distributed.

H₁: Data are not normally distributed.

Therefore, rejecting the statistical null hypothesis (H₀) means that the data were not normal and rejected the null hypothesis if the significance level of the test was less than .050 (sig < 0.05). According to the results of the table and since sig or P-Value was more than 0.05, the null hypothesis could be accepted that the data distribution was normal.

4 Table

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

					One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test
posttest teachers	pretest teachers	posttest students	pretest students		
50	50	20	20		N
3.8240	2.7107	3.6450	2.5717	Mean	Normal Parameters ^{a,b}
.50179	.19982	.27365	.28944	Std. Deviation	
.113	.119	.187	.184	Absolute	Most Extreme Differences
.113	.060	.120	.169	Positive	
-.067	-.119	-.187	-.184	Negative	
.113	.119	.187	.184		Test Statistic
.153 ^c	.076 ^c	.064 ^c	.073 ^c		Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
					a. Test distribution is Normal.
					b. Calculated from data.
					c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

Hypothesis testing

In this section, research questions were examined using the parametric t-test with paired samples (Paired-Sample T Test). T-test with paired samples was used to analyze tests in which each person was observed twice in two different situations. In these experiments, the size of the variable was examined in two positions (before and after). The null hypothesis in the paired data design was that there was no difference between the values of the means in the two paired samples of the population, as opposed to the assumption that there was a difference between the values. The hypotheses of t-test of paired samples were as follows:

H0: There is no difference between the mean values of the two paired samples

H1: There is a difference between the mean values of the two paired samples

The first hypothesis analysis (first research question)

In this section, the following question is answered.

What is Iraqi EFL teachers' attitude toward the use of technology in EFL class?

Due to the normality of the variables, the Paired-Sample T Test was used.

5 Table

Paired Samples Statistics pretest and posttest teachers

					Paired Samples Statistics	
Std. Error Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean			
.02826	.19982	50	2.7107	pretest teachers	Pair 1	
.07096	.50179	50	3.8240	posttest teachers		

In the table above, the average score of teachers to the questionnaire before and after using the technology was showed, and the average score before using the technology was 2.71 and the average score after that were 3.82. The table below showed the correlation of scores that due to the significant level of the test (sig = 0.422), no relationship was seen between two variables.

6 Table

Correlations of pretest and posttest teachers

				Paired Samples Correlations	
Sig.	Correlation	N			
.422	-.116	50	pretest teachers & posttest teachers	Pair 1	

7 Table

Paired Samples Test pretest and posttest teachers

									Paired Samples Test
Sig. (2-tailed)	df	t	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Std. Error Mean	Std. Deviation	Paired Differences Mean		
			Upper	Lower					
0.000	49	-14.026	-0.95383	-1.27284	0.07937	0.56126	-1.11333	pretest teachers - posttest teachers	Pair 1

According to the table above, the significance level of the test was 0.000, which was less than 0.05, and the null hypothesis was rejected, which means that educational technology was effective on teachers, and according to

the average questionnaire in both before and after cases, technology could be the reason which had significantly increased the willingness of teachers.

The second hypothesis analysis (second research question)

In this section, the following question was answered.

What is Iraqi EFL learners' attitude toward the use of technology in EFL class?

Due to the normality of the variables, the Paired-Sample T Test was used.

8 Table

Paired Samples Statistics pretest and posttest Students

					Paired Samples Statistics	
Std. Error Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Mean			
.06472	.28944	20	2.5717	pretest students	Pair 1	
.06119	.27365	20	3.6450	post test students		

In the table above, the average score of students in the questionnaire before and after using the technology was sh, and the average score before and after using the technology was 2.57 , 3.65, respectively. The table below showed the correlation of scores that according to the significance level of the test (sig = 0.000), a positive relationship was seen between the two variables, which was not the subject of this study (and had no application in this study).

9 Table

Paired Samples Correlations between pretest and posttest Students

				Paired Samples Correlations	
Sig.	Correlation	N			
.000	.718	20	pretest students & posttest students	Pair 1	

10 Table

Paired Samples Test pretest and posttest Students

									Paired Samples Test
Sig. (2-tailed)	df	t	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Std. Error Mean	Std. Deviation	Paired Differences Mean		
			Upper	Lower					
.000	19	-22.632	.97407	-1.17259	.04742	.21209	-1.07333	pretest teachers - posttest teachers	Pair 1

According to the table above, the significance level of the test was 0.000, which was less than 0.05, and the null hypothesis was rejected, which meant that educational technology was effective on language learners. Also, it was proved through the average questionnaire technology in both before and after. It had significantly increased the willingness of language learners.

4. Discussion

As data indicated, fifty Iraqi EFL teachers were participated. Among teachers, twenty five were males and twenty five were females. EFL male teachers' attitude in pretest and posttest was 2.72 and 2.74, respectively.

EFL female teachers' attitude in pretest and posttest was 2.70 and 3.91, respectively. In light of the findings, female teachers showed high attitude and to use technology than the male teachers.

Paired Samples Test pretest and posttest teachers showed that the significance level of the test was 0.000, which was less than 0.05, and the null hypothesis was rejected, which means that educational technology was effective on teachers

The current study was also in line with the following studies which claim that learning through video is more interesting. For example, González Contreras (2017) suggests that learning English with aiding video causes learning and interesting together. Above all, learning English with video not only achieves personal instructive needs: it can also make the process of learning more interesting. Similarly, the current study is also in line with the study to which technology makes learning to occur in an interesting way. Galbraith and Rodriguez (2018) indicating that the use of video has a positive effect on the students' engagement in the class. Thus, the integration of novel technology has a significant role in the student's engagement by increasing their participation in learning activities and discussions with their teacher as well as other students in the class. In this meaning, the results support previous studies emphasizing that video is an effective tool for engaging students in learning activities.

According to Rahimi and Yadollahi (2010), a lower technology anxiety had resulted better integration of technology in EFL classrooms; and as older teachers had higher levels of technology anxiety than younger teachers, they were more hesitant to incorporate technology into their classes. It is also reported that external factors such as time constraints, inadequate technology, inflexible school programs and textbooks, and lack of managerial care affect the execution of CALL in a negative way. On the other hand, internal factors such as teachers' inadequacy in technology use, technological knowledge, and views on technology integration also influence teachers' choices to use technology in their classrooms (Park & Son, 2009).

Assessing teachers' performance based on using technology in an educational setting might motivate teachers to work on computers. Teachers were encouraged to use it and to facilitate students' learning. It view might provide teachers with more information regarding technology and curricula, and encourages them to go ahead in using technology.

As data indicated, twenty Iraqi EFL learners were participated. Among learners, twelve were males and eight females. EFL male learners' attitude in pretest and posttest was 2.65 and 3.66, respectively. EFL girl learners' attitude in pretest and posttest was 2.45 and 3.73, respectively. In light of the findings, female students showed high attitude and to use technology than the male students. The improvement of girls was more significant than males. Also, it was proved the view of nowadays youth generation copied with the updated technologies.

As data showed that the significance level of the test was 0.000, which was less than 0.05, and the null hypothesis was rejected, which meant that educational technology was effective on language learners.

Based on the result, teachers must, first, be interested in technology. If they were not interested, then they had to learn it because every teacher has to know about it. It was clear that know all schools in the future will be equipped with technological tools, especially smart boards, so all teachers and teacher candidates must be provided with the necessary knowledge about technology integration in teaching English.

This result could be attributed to the belief that teachers had regarding the use of educational technology, especially in teaching English as a foreign language, i.e. educational technology could be considered as a contemporary means that might help both teachers and students in achieving the objectives of the educational process. This result might be also attributed to the positive attitudes of teachers about technology as the main tools in teaching and learning. From a psychological point of view, using educational technology by teachers, when they teach English language perhaps let them feel more comfortable, could satisfy their needs and achieve their objectives, through using computers in teaching. So, most of English language teachers were interested in using technology, because of their many characteristics in teaching that might support the teachers' efforts in this area. At the same time English language teachers might think that some social issues affect using educational technology in teaching negatively.

According to English language teachers, they thought that educational technology was an essential and significant instrument that should be available in every school, and should take a priority. This result might be also attributed to the positive attitudes of English language teachers toward using educational technology as a tool that might reinforce and encourage students' learning, especially if the students themselves have enough opportunity to use computers inside the classroom, in front of other students. Perhaps, students might enjoy using educational technology, because they found it was interesting and the subject-matter was more interesting.

As well as, English language teachers might think that using educational technology could facilitate learning language, and could be applied in different domains of knowledge, and various activities related to language learning, especially beginning learners who study a foreign language. So teachers, from their experience in using technology, might prefer teaching by using technology on teaching by using the traditional method, because they enjoy using technology, or perhaps they found it more practical, could improve teaching

as well as saving time and effort. So the majority of teachers (especially female teachers) had positive attitudes toward technology and its usage in education in general, and teaching a foreign language in particular. In addition, it might prove as Parvin and Salam (2015) state that despite the positive effects of technology on assisting learners to become autonomous, teachers need to conduct the students by providing instructional support.

Finally, the suggested model of the Iraqi EFL learners' and teachers' attitudes towards using technology enjoy sufficient validity and reliability was confirmed. The reliability statistics indicate that Cronbach's Alpha was found to be 0.79. The reliability and the internal validity of the constructs were diagnosed by the appropriate reliability analysis. The Cronbach's alpha reliability overall scale is 0.79 which was acceptable and none of the items was deleted for further analysis. The reliability analysis results showed that the questionnaire was reliable.

Based on the Confirmatory factor analysis, the following questions got the higher t- value: Q27: I am interested in using technology, Q22: I'd call myself a risk-taker, Q23: I like to practice English the way native speakers do, Q19: By technology, I find it easy to put myself in other people's shoes and imagine how they feel, Q7: I find it hard to make conversation even with people who speak my language but after practicing English by using technology this feeling changed.

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